

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF OBTAINING HIGH-PURE SELENIUM IN THE INDUSTRY AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses pure selenium, which is a solid, colorless substance that has semiconducting properties and is obtained from selenite ore. Pure selenium is used in the production of semiconductor devices, glasses, ceramics, photographic materials, cosmetics, drugs, and alloys. However, it is toxic and needs to be used under limited and controlled conditions. The article also describes various ways to obtain pure selenium, such as reduction of selenites, electrolysis, and laser ablation. The process of obtaining pure selenium is complex, time-consuming, and requires careful safety measures. The article also highlights some of the challenges in the process, including the low concentration of selenium in natural sources, its toxicity, high cost, and limited availability of rare sources. Finally, the article outlines various methods for purifying selenium to a purity level of 99.9% or higher, such as distillation, flotation cleaning, and electrolysis.

Pure selenium (Pure selenium) is a form of elemental selenium, which is a chemical element with atomic number 34 and is represented by the symbol Se. Pure selenium is a solid, colorless substance that has a metallic luster and has semiconducting properties.

Pure selenium can be obtained from selenite ore, where it is often combined with sulfur. It can also be produced electrolytically. Pure selenium has many uses, including the production of semiconductor devices, glasses, ceramics, photographic materials, and cosmetics.

However, it is important to note that pure selenium is toxic when ingested in small amounts. It can cause health problems, including nervous system disorders, liver and kidney damage, and allergic reactions. Therefore, the use of pure selenium should be limited and controlled.

Also, it should be clarified that pure selenium should not be confused with selenium, which is an essential trace element for the human body and is found in many foods.

Selenium is used in many industries and technologies due to its useful properties such as semiconductor, photovoltaic and catalytic properties. Some of the uses for pure selenium are listed below:

1. **Semiconductor Manufacturing:** Selenium is used to make semiconductor devices such as photodiodes, transistors, and solar cells. Selenium has semiconducting properties, which allows it to work as a material from which electronic components are made.
2. **Photography:** Selenium is used in the production of photographic films and paper. In the photographic industry, selenium is used as a sensing element in photovoltaic cells, which convert light into electrical current.
3. **Glass production:** Selenium is used to improve the optical properties of glass. It can be added to glass mass to improve its transparency, corrosion resistance and other properties.
4. **Ceramic production:** Selenium is used as a pigment in the production of ceramic products. It can be added to glazes to give them a yellow or orange color.

5. **Cosmetics:** Selenium is used as an ingredient in cosmetics to improve the condition of the skin and hair. It can help hydrate and brighten the skin, as well as soften the hair.

6. **Drug Manufacturing:** Selenium is used as an ingredient in some drugs. It can help reduce inflammation, improve immune function, and reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease.

7. **Alloy Manufacturing:** Selenium can be added to alloys to improve their strength and corrosion resistance.

However, it should be noted that the use of pure selenium must be controlled, as it is a toxic substance.

Selenium is an element that occurs naturally in the form of minerals such as selenite, claustalite, crocodylite, berzelianite, etc. It can also be obtained in the laboratory in various ways.

One of the most common ways to obtain pure selenium is the reduction of selenites or selenates in the presence of an electron donor such as sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), magnesium (Mg), or sodium hydride (NaH).

The process of obtaining selenium includes the following steps:

1. Grinding a natural mineral containing selenium to obtain a powder.
2. Treatment of the powder with a mixture containing an electron donor such as Na_2CO_3 or Mg.
3. Heating the mixture to a high temperature (about 900-1000 degrees Celsius) to initiate the reduction process.
4. Extraction of pure selenium from the resulting mixture. This can be done by distillation, crystallization, or other methods.

Also, selenium can be obtained by electrolysis of a solution of selenite or selenate in an acidic environment, or by laser ablation of metallic selenium in a vacuum.

In any case, the process of obtaining pure selenium requires precise control of technological parameters and careful safety measures, since selenium is a toxic substance.

Obtaining pure selenium is a rather complex and time-consuming process, which can face several problems.

1. Low concentration of selenium in natural sources. In nature, selenium is usually present in small amounts, which makes it quite difficult to extract and obtain a pure substance.

2. The toxicity of selenium. Selenium is a toxic substance, and the process of obtaining pure selenium requires careful safety measures and precise control of process parameters.

3. The high cost of the acquisition process. Since the process of obtaining pure selenium is complex and laborious, the cost of the process can be quite high.

4. Low efficiency of the receiving process. Due to the fact that selenium is present in nature in small quantities, the process of obtaining pure selenium may have low efficiency, which in turn affects its cost.

5. Limited availability of rare sources of selenium. Some types of selenites containing a high concentration of selenium may be rare and limited in their availability for mining, which in turn affects the process of obtaining pure selenium.

6. The need to use expensive reagents and equipment. Obtaining pure selenium requires the use of special expensive reagents and equipment, which can also increase the cost of the process.

There are several methods for purifying selenium to a purity level of 99.9% or higher. Let's consider some of them:

1. Distillation. This method consists of heating the selenium to its boiling point, where the selenium evaporates and then collects and condenses to give a pure product. However, this method is not always effective in the purification of selenium, as some impurities can also go into the vapor phase and remain in the final product.

2. flotation cleaning. This method is used to remove mineral impurities such as sulfur from ore containing selenium. The ore is placed in a tank of water, to which chemicals are added to form a foam that selects the selenium minerals and other impurities.

3. Electrolysis. This method is used to purify selenium in solution. The solution is placed in an electrolytic tank, where pure selenium is separated at the cathode. This method can be effective if the solution of selenites or selenates contains a small amount of impurities.

4. Crystallization. This method is used to purify selenium from solutions containing selenites or selenates. The solution is cooled so that the selenites or selenates begin to crystallize. The crystals are then separated and can be further purified.

5. Ion-exchange cleaning. This method is used to remove metal ions and other impurities from solutions containing selenium. The solution passes through a column filled with a special resinous material that traps impurity ions, and then selenium is separated from the solution.

6. Oxidation and isolation of selenium as selenate. This method is used to purify selenium from solutions containing selenites. The selenites are oxidized to selenates, and then the selenates are separated from the solution.

Purification of selenium to a purity level of 99.9% can be challenging due to the presence of various impurities in the starting material. However, there are several solutions that can help with this problem:

1. Using a combination of different cleaning methods. Depending on the starting material and the type of impurities, several purification methods can be used to achieve the desired level of purity. For example, flotation cleaning can be used to remove mineral impurities, and then distillation can be used to remove remaining impurities.

2. Optimization of cleaning processes. To improve cleaning performance, process optimizations can be made, such as changing temperatures, times, or adding certain chemicals to improve cleaning.

3. Use of new technologies. There are new technologies that can be used to purify selenium, such as membrane methods, ion exchange methods, or the use of ultrasound. These methods may be more efficient and cost effective.

4. Quality control. To achieve a high level of selenium purity, it is necessary to carry out quality control at each stage of the purification process. This will help identify possible problems and improve the cleaning process.

5. Cooperation with other companies and organizations. In some cases, especially for small and medium-sized companies, it may be beneficial to collaborate with other companies and organizations that have experience in the field of selenium purification. This can help to gain new knowledge and experience that can be applied to improve the cleaning process.

Pure selenium is a solid, colorless substance that has semiconducting properties and can be obtained from selenite ore or produced electrolytically. It has many uses in various industries such as semiconductor manufacturing, glass, ceramics, and cosmetic production, but its use must be controlled due to its toxicity.

Selenium occurs naturally as minerals and can be obtained in the laboratory by reducing selenites or selenates with an electron donor or by electrolysis. The process requires precise control of technological parameters and safety measures due to selenium's toxicity.

Obtaining pure selenium is a complex and time-consuming process with several problems such as the low concentration of selenium in natural sources, selenium's toxicity, high cost, low efficiency, limited availability of rare sources, and the need for expensive reagents and equipment.

Several methods exist for purifying selenium to a purity level of 99.9% or higher, including distillation, flotation cleaning, and electrolysis. However, some impurities

can remain in the final product, and the process requires careful consideration due to the toxicity of selenium.

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